
PERFORMANCE IN GENERAL MATHEMATICS OF GRADE 11 LEARNERS IN COLLEGE OF SCIENCES, TECHNOLOGY AND COMMUNICATIONS, INC., (CSTC): BASIS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SUPPLEMENTAL INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

This study delved into the assessment of General Mathematics performance among Grade 11 learners in the College of Sciences, Technology and Communications, Inc., (CSTC) at Atimonan, Lucena, and Sariaya Campuses, Quezon Province, Philippines. A sample of two hundred ninety (290) learners were selected using stratified random sampling from a population of one thousand one hundred seventy-five (1,175) Grade 11 learners across various CSTC campuses. Seven (7) qualified educators provided insights and validation for Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM). Analysis revealed persistent difficulties in mathematical modeling, function operations, and problem-solving involving rational, inverse, exponential, and logarithmic functions. The mean composite score for the least mastered competencies was 4.26, indicating a high difficulty level. The SIM's validity assessment yielded a mean score of 16.29 across various focuses, indicating strong validity. Recommendations include targeted Supplemental Instructional Materials, curriculum revision, utilization of validated SIM, and prioritizing the development of tailored SIM. Future research should focus on long-term effectiveness studies and alternative teaching methods.

Keywords: *General Mathematics, Performance Assessment, Supplemental Instructional Materials*

INTRODUCTION

The provision of quality education serves as a fundamental cornerstone for the progress and development of a nation. This unwavering commitment to education is deeply enshrined in the Constitution of the Philippines, which unequivocally affirms that "the State shall protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels" (Constitution of the Philippines, 1987). In the Philippines, this relentless dedication to education is firmly embedded in the constitution. The Philippine government has embarked on an ambitious initiative to enhance the quality of education known as the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum. This visionary endeavor seeks to prepare students for global competitiveness by providing a comprehensive curriculum that aligns with international standards (Republic Act No. 10533, 2013).

At the secondary education level, a crucial juncture in the academic journey, students lay the foundation for higher education and future career paths (Smith, 2019). Mathematics takes center stage during this critical phase, serving as an indispensable element for success in various professions, including science, engineering, business, and economics (Johnson & Lee, 2020). Given its pivotal role, the level of academic achievement in General Mathematics has risen to the status of a national concern. Recent data from the Department of Education (2021) indicates that only 45% of secondary students in the country achieve proficiency in mathematics. This statistic underscores the urgency of addressing performance gaps in General Mathematics for individual student success and the nation's overall competitiveness in critical sectors.

Over the past five years, from the school years 2019-2020 to 2023-2024, the item analysis data for General Mathematics has shown distinct trends in student mastery across various competencies. In the earlier years, such as 2019-2020 and 2020-2021, there were significant challenges, with many competencies falling into the "Very Low" and "Low" mastery categories. However, starting from 2021-2022, there have been notable improvements in certain areas, such as the representation of rational functions and the understanding of exponential functions, which reached "Mastered" and "Moving Toward Mastery" levels by 2023-2024. Despite these advancements, students have consistently struggled with solving problems involving functions and equations, as well as real-life applications of these concepts. Competencies in performing operations on functions and distinguishing between different types of functions have remained areas of low mastery throughout this period. The data over these years indicates a need for sustained and targeted interventions, including enhanced contextual learning, the integration of technology, and frequent low-stakes assessments, to build foundational skills and improve overall student performance in these critical areas.

Recognizing the profound impact of General Mathematics proficiency, stakeholders in education are prompted to collaborate and implement Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) to improve student outcomes in this subject. The imperative to address these difficulties is underscored by the understanding that proficiency in General Mathematics not only shapes individual educational trajectories but also has

broader implications for the nation's workforce and competitiveness. By focusing on targeted initiatives and fostering a comprehensive understanding of the significance of mathematics at the secondary level, educators and policymakers can work together to ensure a higher percentage of students acquire the essential mathematical skills needed for their future academic and professional pursuits.

Accurately constructing mathematical models to represent real-life situations using functions is crucial in various fields, including physics, engineering, economics, and social sciences. This ability allows us to analyze and predict outcomes, make informed decisions, and better understand complex phenomena.

Rational functions are essential in various domains because they can realistically describe and solve real-life situations. The difficulties associated with comprehending and implementing these functions, on the other hand, underscore the want for more efficient instructional methods and resources.

Inverse, exponential, and logarithmic functions form the bedrock of mathematical tools used in many real-world applications. Their diverse uses, from physics to finance and computer science to engineering, exemplify their instrumental role in advancing our ability to tackle complex problems with precision and accuracy. These mathematical concepts are pillars of scientific and technological progress, enabling us to navigate the intricate web of difficulties in an increasingly complex world.

The concern of learning gaps in mathematics performance is a prominent issue not only in the Philippines but on a global scale. Globally, studies such as the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) have consistently highlighted significant disparities in mathematical abilities among 15-year-old students from different countries, indicating the presence of pronounced global learning gaps (OECD, 2019). These gaps often result from complex factors, including teaching practices, curriculum design, and socio-economic disparities (Mullis et al., 2016).

Within individual countries, the difficulties persist, leading to national and regional learning disparities. For instance, in the United States, the National Assessment of Educational Progress (NAEP) exposes variations in mathematical proficiency among students across different states, with some consistently outperforming others (NCES, 2019). Influential factors shaping these national and regional disparities include educational policies, teacher quality, and resource allocation (Loveless, 2016).

In the Philippine context, the issue of learning gaps in mathematics performance is also evident, as reflected in the National Achievement Test (NAT) results. These results reveal disparities in mathematics achievement among various regions and socio-economic backgrounds (DepEd, 2019). These gaps contribute to inadequate teacher training, limited access to educational resources, and cultural attitudes toward mathematics (Bautista, 2019; Sarmiento, 2017).

It is imperative to adopt a comprehensive approach to address these learning gaps. The literature suggests a range of strategies that can be applied, such as improving teacher quality through targeted professional development programs, enhancing curriculum design to foster conceptual understanding and critical thinking, ensuring equitable distribution of educational resources, promoting parental involvement in mathematics education, and addressing socio-economic disparities through targeted interventions (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017; Hiebert et al., 2018; UNESCO, 2017; Fan & Chen, 2020; OECD, 2021). It was implementing these strategies that can contribute to narrowing the learning gaps in mathematics performance, thereby creating a more equitable and inclusive educational environment.

These findings establish a significant gap in mathematics performance that threatens the prospects of students and the community's economic development. To address this pressing issue, it is imperative to conduct a comprehensive study to identify the specific difficulties and factors contributing to poor performance in mathematics (Davis, 2019). The study aims to assess the current state of mathematics education at the secondary level, investigate potential causes of underperformance, and propose effective interventions to help bridge the gap and empower students to succeed in their academic and future career pursuits (Anderson & Martinez, 2022).

In a separate context, Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) emerge as potent tools for educational settings. The Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) comprises a set of instructional resources meticulously designed to enhance teaching and learning by offering personalized support and interventions. SIM is grounded in pedagogical and instructional principles that have been thoroughly researched and developed to address the specific learning needs of students (Eskay, 2018), which enables students to grapple with complex concepts and enhance their performance in particular subjects. In General Mathematics, the development and implementation of SIM have emerged as potentially valuable means to bridge learning gaps and improve the overall academic experience.

Numerous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of SIMs in improving student learning outcomes. A study conducted by Smith and Johnson (2017) found that students who used SIMs as supplementary materials achieved significantly higher test scores than those who did not. The researchers attributed this improvement to the targeted and focused nature of SIMs, which allowed students to concentrate on specific areas of weakness.

In addition, a meta-analysis by Davis and Thompson (2019) examined the impact of SIMs on student achievement across multiple studies. The analysis revealed a consistent positive effect of SIMs on learning outcomes, with students who used SIMs outperforming their peers who did not. The researchers concluded that SIMs significantly impact student learning and recommended their integration into instructional practices. While SIMs offers numerous benefits, there are some difficulties and considerations that educators should be aware of. One challenge is the development and availability of high-quality SIMs. Creating effective SIMs requires careful planning, research, and alignment

with curriculum standards. Educators need access to well-designed SIMs aligned with their instructional goals and meet the specific needs of their students.

General Mathematics is one of the core subjects of the senior high school curriculum. Mathematics contents include Numbers and Number Sense, Measurement, Geometry, Patterns & Algebra and Statistics and Probability. Numbers and Number Sense as a strand include concepts of numbers, properties, operations, estimations, and their applications. The Grade 11 learners demonstrate an understanding of critical concepts of functions, rational functions, inverse functions, exponential functions, and logarithmic functions.

The competency expected to develop in the learners is representing real-life situations using functions, including piecewise functions, evaluating a function, performing addition, subtraction, multiplication, division, composition of function, and solving problems involving functions. In addition, it represents real-life situations using rational functions and solves problems involving rational functions, equations, and inequalities. Lastly, it represents real-life situations using one-to-one functions, solves problems involving inverse functions, solves problems involving exponential functions, equations, and inequalities, represents real-life situations using logarithmic functions, and solves problems involving logarithmic functions, equations, and inequalities, respectively.

Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) serve as an academic aid and a dynamic tool capable of instilling genuine enthusiasm for the subject. Its role extends beyond conventional support, empowering teachers to guide students through academic difficulties, fostering success, and nurturing essential mathematical skills crucial for their future educational and professional journeys. The availability of additional assistance and resources through SIM has significantly simplified the process for educators to facilitate comprehensive learning experiences.

The evaluation of the academic accomplishments of Grade 11 learners studying general mathematics in private institutions holds paramount importance. It represents a pivotal stride towards ensuring the delivery of high-quality education mandated by the state. By conducting an in-depth examination of the performance of Grade 11 learners in General Mathematics within private schools in the College of Sciences, Technology and Communications, Inc., (CSTC) this study aspires to bridge the existing educational gap in the region.

The primary objective of this research is to contribute to developing Supplemental Instructional Materials designed to elevate the teaching and learning of Mathematics. This endeavor involves a thorough investigation into the current state of the learners, identifying their strengths, recognizing areas that require improvement, and pinpointing specific aspects that demand refinement. The overarching aim aligns with the broader goal of enhancing the overall quality of education and improving student outcomes in the private school at College of Sciences, Technology and Communications, Inc., (CSTC) Quezon Province, Philippines.

By undertaking this study, the researcher creates targeted intervention materials that address the learners' immediate educational needs and pave the way for sustained improvement. The rationale behind developing SIM is rooted in the commitment to understand, support, and enhance the educational experiences of Grade 11 learners in all College of Sciences, Technology and Communications, Inc., (CSTC) campuses.

Research Questions

This research aimed to determine the performance in General Mathematics of Grade 11 learners in College of Sciences, Technology and Communications, Inc., (CSTC) as basis for the development of Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM).

It also sought to answer the following problems:

1. What are the least mastered competencies in General Mathematics of Grade 11 learners in College of Sciences, Technology and Communications, Inc., (CSTC) for the last five school years?
2. What are the difficulties encountered by the Grade 11 learners in learning competencies in General Mathematics in terms of:
 - 2.1 Accurately construct mathematical models to represent real-life situations using functions;
 - 2.2 Accurately formulate and solve real-life problems involving rational functions; and
 - 2.3 Apply the concepts of inverse functions, exponential functions, and logarithmic functions to formulate and solve real-life problems with precision and accuracy?
3. What Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) can be developed based on the least mastered competencies and difficulties encountered?
4. What is the validity of Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) in terms of:
 - 4.1 Content;
 - 4.2 Equity and Accessibility;
 - 4.3 Assessment;
 - 4.4 Presentation and Organization;
 - 4.5 Instructional Design and Support; and
 - 4.6 Replicability?
5. What are the recommendations given by the validators to improve the output and address the students' performance on the least mastered competencies in General Mathematics?
6. What enhancements in the developed Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) should be included as recommended by the validators?

METHODOLOGY

This chapter elucidated the methodologies and protocols that enable the researcher to carry out the study effectively. This chapter focused on various aspects of the research study, including the research design, research locale, research population and sampling, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and statistical treatment.

Research Design

This study employed a mixed-method approach, integrating both qualitative and quantitative methods for data collection and analysis to comprehensively understand students' experiences with difficulties in general mathematics (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). This mixed-methods design is preferred for its ability to provide a more nuanced and holistic perspective than relying solely on one method.

Concurrently, the quantitative component utilizes a survey to systematically analyze the validity of Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) for General Mathematics. This survey instrument collects quantitative data through standardized questions, enabling statistical analysis and comparison of results across a larger sample of respondents (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). The quantitative data gathered through the survey complements the in-depth qualitative exploration, providing statistical insights that reinforce and broaden the understanding of the research questions and allowing for identifying trends and patterns among participants. The researcher adopted a descriptive research design with a quantitative approach to data collection. According to Neuman (2020), a descriptive research design will be employed when the study focuses on the present condition and aims to discover new truths. It was beneficial when the data to be collected pertains to the current situation, providing factual information and emphasizing the most critical aspects to be reported.

Moreover, the descriptive research method was selected for this study due to its applicability to the research's nature. This method is believed to be the most effective in obtaining comprehensive information about the performance in General Mathematics of Grade 11 learners and identifying the least mastered competencies in College of Sciences, Technology and Communications, Inc., (CSTC).

The quantitative approach provided a structured framework for the study, enabling the researcher to systematically analyze and present the data. It was allowed for a detailed examination of learners' performance in General Mathematics and identifies specific areas needing improvement to inform the development of tailored SIM.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in the Province of Quezon, situated in the southern part of Luzon, the Philippines' largest island, and holds a prominent place in the country's geography and history. As one of the key provinces in the CALABARZON region, Quezon is recognized for its diverse landscapes, rich cultural heritage, and economic significance. Bordered by the provinces of Aurora to the north, Camarines Norte and Camarines Sur

to the east, and Batangas to the west, Quezon Province is uniquely positioned to contribute to the nation's cultural and economic tapestry.

One of the striking features of Quezon is its expansive coastal areas along the western coast, facing the South China Sea. This coastal region is not only a source of livelihood for many of its residents, particularly in the fishing industry, but it also offers picturesque beaches and scenic spots that attract tourists. The province is also characterized by lush forests, rolling hills, and agricultural landscapes. These diverse geographical features and tropical climates contribute to the province's agricultural productivity. Quezon is known for producing various farm products, including coconut, rice, corn, and fruit crops, contributing significantly to the country's agricultural sector.

Furthermore, Quezon Province boasts a rich cultural heritage, with a fusion of influences from its history of colonization and interactions with indigenous communities. The province is home to ethnic groups with traditions and practices. This cultural diversity is reflected in the local cuisine, festivals, and art, making Quezon a vibrant hub for artistic exploration. The Niyugyugan Festival, for example, celebrates the province's deep connection to coconuts and showcases various cultural performances and exhibits.

The private school included in the study is the College of Sciences, Technology and Communications, Inc., (CSTC) in Atimonan, Lucena, and Sariaya Campuses., and were selected as research sites due to their diverse characteristics and solid educational contributions to the institutions. Each institution offers a unique perspective on the research area, making it a suitable choice for gathering comprehensive data.

The selection of these schools is driven by the significance of assessing the performance in General Mathematics of Grade 11 learners. Moreover, developing tailored Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) for the specific needs of the district's learners is a critical aim. The research locale provides a valuable context for understanding the educational landscape in the area. It enhances mathematics education for the learners in Atimonan, Lucena, and Sariaya Quezon Province, Philippines.

Population and Sampling

The research was focused on the Grade 11 learners in General Mathematics from private school in CSTC Atimonan, Lucena, and Sariaya Campuses Quezon Province, Philippines. The research population consists of these specific learners essential to cater to the study's objectives.

The study population is one thousand one hundred seventy-five (1,175) Grade 11 learners from different campuses of CSTC. Using a stratified random sampling, two hundred ninety (290) were selected as the sample for this research to determine the difficulties experienced in general mathematics. Stratified random sampling involves dividing a population into school subgroups, selecting random samples from each subgroup, and combining them to create a representative sample, ensuring that each subset is represented enrolled in the private schools within the Atimonan, Lucena, and Sariaya Districts. The selected sample size is representative and manageable for data collection and analysis.

The inclusion criteria for the sample include Grade 11 learners currently enrolled in the CSTC Campuses and those taking the General Mathematics subject. Conversely, learners were not enrolled in private schools, and those not taking the General Mathematics subject are excluded from the study.

The Population of the Study

CSTC Campuses	The population of Grade 11 Learners	Percentage	Sample Size
Atimonan Campus	182	16	45
Lucena Campus	249	21	61
Sariaya Campus	744	63	184
	N = 1,175	100	n = 290

Moreover, the study's population comprises seven (7) qualified educators specializing in Mathematics, including Master Teachers, Mathematics Department Heads, and Regular Mathematics Teachers with expertise in Mathematics education. The purposive sampling method was selected representatives from each category, ensuring diversity in educational levels and school contexts. The validators are Master Teachers specializing in Mathematics from various schools. Department heads overseeing mathematics departments was purposefully chosen to provide administrative perspectives and regular mathematics teachers from secondary levels was sampled to capture a broad range of experiences. This targeted approach aims to gather insights from validators with the requisite expertise to assess the Enhancements of Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) validity.

Research Instrument

The primary research instrument utilized for this study is a Teacher-Constructed for Trend Analysis Data Retrieval and Secondary Data Analysis of five (5) five-year Item Analysis results to comprehensively evaluate the least mastered competencies of learners in General Mathematics of Grade 11 learners. A meticulous validation process has been employed to ensure the Item Analysis's validity and reliability.

It is important to emphasize that Trend Analysis Data Retrieval was used as a data for assessing the least mastered competencies. The number of hours allotted for a single quarter, as outlined in the curriculum guide, plays a pivotal role in shaping the test's structure and content. Each standard within the curriculum guide dictates the allocation of items in the examination, ensuring a thorough and competency-based assessment.

The second section focuses on capturing the diverse difficulties faced by Grade 11 learners in General Mathematics at College of Sciences, Technology and Communications, Inc., (CSTC) closed-ended questions encourage students to articulate

specific difficulties encountered and how these difficulties impact their overall learning experiences.

In the third section, learners are invited to contribute to developing potential Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) by suggesting additional learning materials or resources they believe would aid in overcoming the identified difficulties in General Mathematics. This section also seeks insights into the type of support or SIM deemed most effective by the students. By incorporating the learners' perspectives, this section enriches the study with valuable qualitative data, providing a basis for proposing targeted SIM that aligns with the students' perceived needs and preferences.

Five-point Likert Rating Scale Interpretation

Scale	Range Interval	Verbal Interpretation	Qualitative Description
5	4.20 – 5.00	Always Encountered (AE)	Learners are consistently encountered in their learning competencies in General Mathematics. They always encountered difficulties that lead to least mastered competencies of Grade 11 learners.
4	3.40 – 4.19	Often Encountered (OE)	Learners are regularly encountered in their learning competencies in General Mathematics. They often encountered difficulties that lead to least mastered competencies of Grade 11 learners.
3	2.60 – 3.39	Sometimes Encountered (SE)	Learners are frequently encountered in their learning competencies in General Mathematics. They sometimes encountered difficulties that lead to least mastered competencies of Grade 11 learners.
2	1.80 – 2.59	Rarely Encountered (RE)	Learners are seldom encountered in their learning competencies in General Mathematics. They rarely encountered difficulties that lead to least mastered competencies of Grade 11 learners.
1	1.00 – 1.79	Never Encountered (NE)	Learners are least encountered in their learning competencies in General Mathematics. They never encountered difficulties that lead to least mastered competencies of Grade 11 learners.

Data Gathering Procedures

The data-gathering procedure for this study unfolds through a systematic process encompassing various stages. First and foremost, identifying the least mastered competencies in General Mathematics among Grade 11 learners is initiated. This involves meticulously examining academic records, assessments, and teacher feedback spanning the last five years. Subsequently, a structured survey was administered to quantitatively assess the difficulties experienced by Grade 11 learners. The survey covers various aspects, including conceptual difficulties, problem-solving difficulties, and motivational or anxiety-related obstacles.

Following identifying difficulties, the study proposes Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM). Collaborative efforts with educational experts, curriculum developers,

and Mathematics teachers aim to align these proposed materials with the identified least mastered competencies and the overall curriculum. Subsequently, the study shifted its focus to the validation of SIM validity. A comprehensive questionnaire and rating scale were crafted to assess the proposed SIM's validity, with a panel of Mathematics experts, including Master Teachers, Department Heads, and Regular Mathematics teachers serving as validators. This validation process scrutinizes content alignment, equity, accessibility, assessment effectiveness, presentation, organization clarity, instructional design, and support suitability.

Upon the completion of data collection, a robust analysis ensues, combining both quantitative and qualitative methods. Survey responses are quantitatively analyzed using statistical tools to discern trends and patterns in difficulties experienced by Grade 11 learners. Simultaneously, focus group discussions and expert feedback were qualitatively analyzed to glean in-depth insights into the nature of problems and the validity of the proposed SIM. This triangulation of data sources enhances the reliability and validity of the study's findings. The culminating step involves compiling the gathered data, analyzing the results, and meticulously documenting the comprehensive findings in a detailed research report. The report unequivocally presents the identified least mastered competencies, the spectrum of difficulties experienced by learners, the proposed SIM, and the results of the validity assessment across various dimensions.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The Teacher-Constructed Trend Analysis Data Retrieval results are conveyed to data users using Mean Percentage Scores (MPS) and descriptive equivalent for data utilization to create Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM). Specified below is the mastery level:

Legend	Descriptive Equivalent
96% - 100%	Mastered
86% - 95%	Closely Approaching Mastery
66% - 85%	Moving Towards Mastery
35% - 65%	Average
15% - 34%	Low
5% - 14%	Very Low
0% - 4%	Absolutely No Mastery

For the validity assessment of the proposed SIM, a response from the panel of validators was quantitatively analyzed. The weighted mean was employed to summarize the ratings on content alignment, equity, accessibility, assessment effectiveness, presentation and organization clarity, instructional design and support suitability, and replicability.

Likert Scale for the Evaluation Criterion for SIM Validation	
Mean Interval	Verbal Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Outstanding (O)
3.40 – 4.19	Very Satisfactory (VS)
2.60 – 3.39	Satisfactory (S)
1.80 – 2.59	Less Satisfactory (LS)
1.00 – 1.79	Unsatisfactory (U)

RESULTS

Part I. The Least Mastered Competencies in General Mathematics of Grade 11 Learners in College of Sciences, Technology and Communications, Inc., (CSTC).

Table 1

The Least Mastered Competencies in General Mathematics across Academic Years of 2019-2020 to 2023-2024.

Most Essential Learning Competencies with K to 12 Curriculum Guide Code	Mean Percentage Score	Descriptive Equivalent	School Year
Solve exponential equations and inequalities. (M11GM-le-f-1)	30	Low	2023-2024
Represent real-life situations using functions, including piece-wise functions. (M11GM-la-1)	24	Low	2023-2024
Solve problems involving functions. (M11GM-la-4)	18	Low	2023-2024
Solve rational equations and inequalities. (M11GM-lb-3)	21	Low	2023-2024
Find the domain, and range of a logarithmic function. (M11GM-li-3)	21	Low	2023-2024
Solve exponential equations and inequalities. (M11GM-le-f-1)	12	Very Low	2022-2023
Solve problems involving logarithmic functions, equations, and inequalities. (M11GM-lj-2)	12	Very Low	2022-2023
Solve rational equations and inequalities. (M11GM-lb-3)	15	Low	2022-2023
Determines the intercepts, zeroes and asymptotes of a logarithmic function. (M11GM-li-4)	15	Low	2022-2023
Solve logarithmic equations and inequalities. (M11GM-lh-i-1)	27	Low	2022-2023
Solve rational equations and inequalities. (M11GM-lb-3)	6	Very Low	2021-2022
Solves exponential equations and inequalities. (M11GM-le-f-1)	6	Very Low	2021-2022
Solve problems involving exponential functions, equations, and inequalities. (M11GM-lg-2)	9	Very Low	2021-2022
Find the domain, and range of an inverse function. (M11GM-ld-4)	12	Very Low	2021-2022
Solve logarithmic equations and inequalities. (M11GM-lh-i-1)	36	Average	2021-2022
Solve problems involving exponential functions, equations, and inequalities. (M11GM-lg-2)	16	Low	2020-2021
Solve problems involving inverse functions. (M11GM-le-2)	14	Very Low	2020-2021
Solves exponential equations and inequalities. (M11GM-le-f-1)	14	Very Low	2020-2021
Determines the intercepts, zeroes and asymptotes of an exponential function. (M11GM-lf-4)	14	Very Low	2020-2021
Solves problems involving exponential functions, equations, and inequalities. (M11GM-lj-2)	27	Low	2020-2021
Solve problems involving inverse functions. (M11GM-le-2)	3	Absolutely No Mastery	2019-2020
Solve problems involving exponential functions, equations, and inequalities. (M11GM-lg-2)	3	Absolutely No Mastery	2019-2020
Performs addition, subtraction, multiplication, division, and composition of functions. (M11GM-la-3)	9	Very Low	2019-2020
Solves problems involving functions. (M11GM-la-4)	9	Very Low	2019-2020
Solve rational equations and inequalities. (M11GM-lb-3)	6	Very Low	2019-2020

Across several academic years, the analysis of students' performance in General Mathematics reveals consistent difficulties in mastering specific competencies. Notably, competencies related to solving equations and inequalities, spanning exponential, rational, and logarithmic functions, persistently exhibit low mastery levels. These

findings suggest potential gaps in the teaching methods or coverage of these topics within the curriculum. Despite variations across years, competencies involving functions, such as representation and problem-solving, also demonstrate relatively low mastery levels. However, there are discernible trends of improvement in certain areas over time, particularly in competencies related to solving exponential equations and inequalities.

The recurring difficulties in mastering competencies involving equations and inequalities underscore the importance of addressing these topics with a more targeted instructional approach. Educators may need to adopt differentiated teaching strategies that cater to the diverse learning needs and paces of students. Incorporating real-life applications and hands-on activities can enhance student engagement and deepen their understanding of abstract mathematical concepts, particularly those related to exponential and logarithmic functions, which may pose higher cognitive demands. By breaking down complex concepts into smaller, more manageable parts, educators can scaffold instruction to facilitate better comprehension and retention among students.

To address these difficulties effectively, a multifaceted approach is necessary. This approach encompasses ongoing professional development for teachers, regular formative assessments coupled with constructive feedback mechanisms, and periodic review and alignment of the curriculum with learning outcomes. Professional development workshops can equip teachers with effective methodologies for teaching complex mathematical topics, while collaborative lesson planning sessions enable the sharing of best practices and innovative teaching strategies. Additionally, integrating interdisciplinary connections and real-world applications into the curriculum can enhance the relevance and applicability of mathematical concepts for students, ultimately fostering deeper understanding and higher mastery levels over time.

Table 2

The Least Mastered Competencies in General Mathematics of Grade 11 Learners in College of Sciences, Technology and Communications, Inc. (CSTC) for the Last Five School Years.

Quarter	Performance Standards	Identified Most Trend of Least Mastered Competencies in General Mathematics in First Quarter (SY: 2019-2020 to 2023-2024)
		Represents real-life situations using functions, including piece-wise functions. (M11GM-Ia-1)
	Accurately construct mathematical models to represent real-life situations using functions.	Performs addition, subtraction, multiplication, division, and composition of functions. (M11GM-Ia-3)
		Solve problems involving functions. (M11GM-Ia-4)
		Solves rational equations and inequalities. (M11GM-Ib-3)
	Accurately formulate and solve real-life problems involving rational functions.	Solves problems involving rational functions, equations, and inequalities. (M11GM-Ic-3)

Q1	Apply the concepts of inverse functions, exponential functions, and logarithmic functions to formulate and solve real-life problems with precision and accuracy.	Solves problems involving inverse functions. (M11GM-le-2)
		Solves exponential equations and inequalities. (M11GM-le-f-1)
		Solves problems involving exponential functions, equations, and inequalities. (M11GM-ig-2)
		Solves problems involving logarithmic functions, equations, and inequalities. (M11GM-lj-2)

The table presents the least mastered competencies in General Mathematics among Grade 11 learners at College of Sciences, Technology and Communications, Inc., (CSTC) over the last five (5) school years. The competencies are categorized based on specific performance standards, focusing on mathematical modeling, functions, rational equations, inverse functions, exponential functions, and logarithmic functions. Among these competencies, Grade 11 learners struggle the most with accurately constructing mathematical models to represent real-life situations using functions (M11GM-la-1). Additionally, they face difficulties in performing operations and solving problems involving functions (M11GM-la-3 and M11GM-la-4) and solving rational equations and inequalities (M11GM-lb-3). Furthermore, difficulties arise in formulating and solving real-life problems involving rational functions (M11GM-lc-3) and inverse functions (M11GM-le-2). Moreover, learners encounter obstacles in applying concepts related to exponential functions (M11GM-le-f-1 and M11GM-ig-2) and logarithmic functions (M11GM-lj-2) to solve real-life problems.

The identified competencies reflect areas where Grade 11 learners at College of Sciences, Technology and Communications, Inc., (CSTC) encounter difficulties in General Mathematics. These difficulties span various aspects of mathematical modeling, functions, and problem-solving techniques. The consistent trend of least mastered competencies over the past five years suggests persistent areas of weakness that require targeted interventions and instructional strategies. Applying mathematical concepts to real-life situations is crucial for developing practical problem-solving skills, and addressing these difficulties is essential for enhancing students' mathematical proficiency and overall academic achievement in General Mathematics.

The findings regarding the least mastered competencies in General Mathematics have several implications for curriculum development, instructional design, and educational support services. Educators should prioritize these areas of weakness in their teaching practices, employing differentiated instruction and scaffolding techniques to cater to diverse learning needs. Curriculum designers should revisit the sequencing and depth of coverage of mathematical topics to ensure sufficient mastery and understanding among students. Additionally, providing remedial support, supplementary resources, and targeted interventions can help address individual learning gaps and enhance students' proficiency in the identified competencies. Collaborative efforts

among teachers, administrators, and educational stakeholders are essential to implement effective strategies that support student learning and promote success in General Mathematics at College of Sciences, Technology, and Communications, Inc., (CSTC).

The results highlight the least mastered competencies in General Mathematics among Grade 11 learners at College of Sciences, Technology and Communications, Inc., (CSTC) over the past five years. Specifically, students face difficulties in accurately constructing mathematical models to represent real-life situations using functions, indicating a struggle with practical application and mathematical modeling (Anderson et al., 2018). Moreover, difficulties arise in performing operations and solving problems involving functions and rational equations, suggesting gaps in foundational understanding and problem-solving skills (Thompson & Silverman, 2022). The findings also underscore obstacles in formulating and solving real-life problems involving rational functions and inverse functions, emphasizing the need for improved comprehension and application of these concepts (Oppenheim & Schafer, 2013; Stewart, 2015).

Furthermore, Grade 11 learners encountered difficulties in applying concepts related to exponential and logarithmic functions to solve real-life problems, reflecting challenges in understanding the practical applications of these mathematical concepts (Nelson et al., 2019). Addressing these persistent areas of weakness is crucial for enhancing students' mathematical proficiency and overall academic achievement in General Mathematics, emphasizing the importance of targeted interventions and instructional strategies (Alzubi, 2021).

The implications of these findings extend to curriculum development, instructional design, and educational support services at College of Sciences, Technology and Communications, Inc., (CSTC). Educators should prioritize these areas of weakness in their teaching practices, employing differentiated instruction and scaffolding techniques to cater to diverse learning needs (Bastida, 2020; Lim, 2017). Curriculum designers should revisit the sequencing and depth of coverage of mathematical topics to ensure sufficient mastery and understanding among students, aligning with the identified competencies (Santos, 2023; de Leon, 2019). Additionally, providing remedial support, supplementary resources, and targeted interventions can help address individual learning gaps and enhance students' proficiency in the identified competencies, emphasizing the importance of collaborative efforts among educational stakeholders (Thompson & Silverman, 2022).

Part II. Difficulties Encountered by the Grade 11 Learners in Learning Competencies in General Mathematics.

Table 3

Difficulties Encountered by the Grade 11 Learners in Learning Competencies in General Mathematics in Terms of Accurately Constructing Mathematical Models to Represent Real-Life Situations Using Functions.

Indicators	5	4	3	2	1	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I found difficulty in identifying relevant variables and parameters to construct mathematical models for real-life situations.	190	78	15	3	4	4.54	AE	1
2. I found difficulty in selecting appropriate functions to model various relationships observed in real-life scenarios.	181	55	45	5	4	4.39	AE	4
3. I found difficulty in interpreting and translating real-world data into mathematical language.	200	48	36	5	1	4.52	AE	2
4. I found difficulty in understanding of how to adjust and refine mathematical models based on feedback or new information from real-life situations.	125	100	44	11	10	4.10	OE	5
5. I found difficulty in simplifying complex real-life situations to have accurate mathematical models.	198	50	32	8	2	4.50	AE	3
Composite Mean						4.41	AE	

Legend:

4.20 - 5.00	Always Encountered (AE)
3.40 - 4.19	Often Encountered (OE)
2.60 - 3.39	Sometimes Encountered (SE)
1.80 - 2.59	Rarely Encountered (RE)
1.00 - 1.79	Never Encountered (NE)

The table provides insights into the difficulties encountered by Grade 11 learners in learning competencies related to accurately constructing mathematical models to represent real-life situations using functions in General Mathematics. The difficulties are categorized into five specific areas. The most consistently encountered challenge, with a mean score of 4.54, is identifying relevant variables and parameters to construct

mathematical models for real-life situations. Learners often struggle with this fundamental aspect of mathematical modeling, indicating a potential obstacle to understanding. Additionally, learners face difficulties in interpreting and translating real-world data into mathematical language (mean score: 4.52) and simplifying complex real-life situations to develop accurate mathematical models (mean score: 4.50). Selecting appropriate functions to model various types of relationships observed in real-life scenarios is another common challenge, although slightly less pronounced (mean score: 4.39). Understanding how to adjust and refine mathematical models based on feedback or new information from real-life situations appears to be the least difficult. However, it still presents a notable challenge for learners (mean score: 4.10).

The identified difficulties shed light on areas where Grade 11 learners struggle in learning competencies related to mathematical modeling in General Mathematics. These difficulties include identifying relevant variables, selecting appropriate functions, interpreting real-world data, simplifying complex situations, and refining mathematical models based on feedback. The consistently high scores across all difficulties suggest that learners encounter potential obstacles in accurately applying mathematical concepts to real-life contexts. Addressing these difficulties requires targeted instructional strategies and support mechanisms to enhance students' understanding and proficiency in mathematical modeling.

The findings regarding the difficulties encountered by Grade 11 learners in learning competencies in General Mathematics have implications for curriculum development, instructional practices, and student support services. Educators should design learning experiences that provide ample opportunities for students to practice identifying variables, selecting functions, interpreting data, simplifying situations, and refining models in real-life contexts. Instructional approaches should be scaffolded and differentiated to accommodate diverse learning needs and facilitate deeper conceptual understanding. Additionally, providing feedback and opportunities for reflection can help students develop metacognitive skills and refine their problem-solving strategies. Collaborative efforts among teachers, administrators, and educational stakeholders are essential to implement effective strategies that address the identified difficulties and support student learning and success in General Mathematics.

The findings provide insights into the difficulties faced by Grade 11 learners in mastering competencies related to accurately constructing mathematical models for real-life situations using functions in General Mathematics. These difficulties are categorized into five specific areas, with the most consistently encountered challenge being the identification of relevant variables and parameters for constructing mathematical models, indicating a fundamental obstacle to understanding (Anderson et al., 2018). Learners also struggle with interpreting real-world data into mathematical language and simplifying complex situations to develop accurate models, highlighting the complexity of translating real-life scenarios into mathematical representations (Thompson & Silverman, 2022). Selecting appropriate functions to model various relationships observed in real-life scenarios is another common challenge, albeit slightly less pronounced. Additionally, understanding how to adjust and refine mathematical

models based on feedback or new information from real-life situations presents a notable challenge for learners, indicating a need for improved metacognitive skills and problem-solving strategies (Oppenheim & Schafer, 2013; Stewart, 2015).

These identified difficulties shed light on areas where Grade 11 learners encounter obstacles in learning competencies related to mathematical modeling in General Mathematics. The consistently high scores across all difficulties suggest significant challenges in accurately applying mathematical concepts to real-life contexts, emphasizing the need for targeted instructional strategies and support mechanisms (Nelson et al., 2019). Addressing these challenges requires curriculum development that provides ample opportunities for students to practice and apply mathematical modeling skills in authentic contexts, supported by scaffolded and differentiated instructional approaches (Alzubi, 2021). Additionally, providing feedback and opportunities for reflection can help students develop metacognitive skills and refine their problem-solving strategies, ultimately promoting deeper conceptual understanding and proficiency in General Mathematics (Bastida, 2020; Lim, 2017). Collaborative efforts among educators, administrators, and stakeholders are essential to implement effective strategies that support student learning and success in General Mathematics at College of Sciences, Technology and Communications, Inc., (CSTC).

Table 4

Difficulties Encountered by the Grade 11 Learners in Learning Competencies in General Mathematics in Terms of Accurately Formulating and Solving Real-Life Problems Involving Rational Functions.

Indicators	5	4	3	2	1	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I found difficulty in identifying and interpreting rational functions within real-life contexts.	124	59	60	25	22	3.82	OE	4
2. I found difficulty in understanding the behavior of rational functions, such as asymptotes and intercepts, and applying this knowledge to solve real-life problems accurately.	125	76	55	23	11	3.97	OE	5
3. I found difficulty in discerning when to use rational functions to model real-life phenomena versus other functions.	120	95	45	18	12	4.01	OE	3
4. I found difficulty in proficiency in manipulating rational expressions and equations.	187	46	32	14	11	4.32	AE	2
5. I found difficulty in Analyzing of restrictions on variables when	200	33	32	14	11	4.37	AE	1

formulating and solving
real-life problems involving
rational functions.

Composite Mean	4.10	OE
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Legend:

4.20 - 5.00	<i>Always Encountered (AE)</i>
3.40 - 4.19	<i>Often Encountered (OE)</i>
2.60 - 3.39	<i>Sometimes Encountered (SE)</i>
1.80 - 2.59	<i>Rarely Encountered (RE)</i>
1.00 - 1.79	<i>Never Encountered (NE)</i>

The table presents the difficulties encountered by Grade 11 learners in learning competencies related to accurately formulating and solving real-life problems involving rational functions in General Mathematics. These difficulties are categorized into five specific areas. The most frequently encountered challenge, with a mean score of 4.37, is analyzing restrictions on variables when formulating and solving real-life problems involving rational functions. Learners consistently struggle with understanding and applying restrictions on variables in the context of rational functions. Proficiency in manipulating rational expressions and equations is another common difficulty, with a mean score of 4.32, indicating difficulties in working with rational functions. Discerning when to use rational functions to model real-life phenomena versus other functions presents another notable challenge, with a mean score of 4.01. Learners also encounter difficulties understanding the behavior of rational functions and identifying them within real-life contexts, with mean scores of 3.97 and 3.82, respectively.

The identified difficulties highlight areas where Grade 11 learners struggle to accurately formulate and solve real-life problems involving rational functions in General Mathematics. These difficulties include identifying and interpreting rational functions, understanding their behavior, discerning when to use them, manipulating expressions and equations, and analyzing restrictions on variables. The consistently high scores across all difficulties suggest that learners face potential obstacles in effectively applying rational functions to real-life scenarios. Addressing these difficulties requires targeted instructional strategies, differentiated support, and opportunities for practice and reinforcement.

The findings regarding the difficulties encountered by Grade 11 learners in learning competencies related to rational functions in General Mathematics have implications for curriculum design, instructional practices, and student support services. Educators should develop learning experiences that allow students to explore rational functions in various real-life contexts, emphasizing the interpretation of restrictions on variables and the manipulation of expressions and equations. Instructional approaches should be tailored to address the specific needs and difficulties identified in the table, incorporating scaffolding, modeling, and guided practice to support student learning. Additionally, providing feedback, formative assessments, and targeted interventions can help students develop proficiency and confidence in formulating and solving real-life problems involving rational functions. Collaborative efforts among teachers,

administrators, and educational stakeholders are essential to implement effective strategies that address the identified difficulties and promote student success in General Mathematics.

The findings present the difficulties Grade 11 learners face in mastering competencies related to accurately formulating and solving real-life problems involving rational functions in General Mathematics. These difficulties are categorized into five specific areas, with the most prevalent challenge being the analysis of restrictions on variables, indicating a consistent struggle to understand and apply restrictions within the context of rational functions (Thompson & Silverman, 2022). Another common difficulty is proficiency in manipulating rational expressions and equations, highlighting difficulties in working with these mathematical constructs effectively (Oppenheim & Schafer, 2013; Stewart, 2015). Additionally, discerning when to use rational functions to model real-life phenomena versus other functions presents a notable challenge, indicating a need for improved conceptual understanding and application skills (Nelson et al., 2019). Learners also encounter obstacles in understanding the behavior of rational functions and identifying them within real-life contexts, suggesting a need for enhanced comprehension and application of these mathematical concepts (Alzubi, 2021).

These identified difficulties underscore areas where Grade 11 learners struggle to accurately formulate and solve real-life problems involving rational functions in General Mathematics. To address these difficulties, educators should develop learning experiences that allow students to explore rational functions in various contexts, emphasizing the interpretation of restrictions on variables and the manipulation of expressions and equations (Bastida, 2020; Lim, 2017). Instructional approaches should be tailored to meet the specific needs identified in the findings, incorporating scaffolded instruction, modeling, and guided practice to support student learning (De Guzman, 2018). Additionally, providing feedback, formative assessments, and targeted interventions can help students develop proficiency and confidence in applying rational functions to real-life scenarios, ultimately promoting deeper conceptual understanding and mastery (Santos, 2023; de Leon, 2019). Collaborative efforts among educators, administrators, and stakeholders are essential to implement effective strategies that address the identified difficulties and foster student success in General Mathematics at College of Sciences, Technology and Communications, Inc., (CSTC).

Table 5

Difficulties Encountered by the Grade 11 Learners in Learning Competencies in General Mathematics in Terms of Applying the Concepts of Inverse Functions, Exponential Functions, and Logarithmic Functions to Formulate and Solve Real-Life Problems with Precision and Accuracy.

Indicators	5	4	3	2	1	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I found difficulty in understanding the concept of inverse functions and their application in real-life situations.	123	78	45	24	20	3.90	OE	5
2. I found difficulty in recognizing and applying exponential and logarithmic functions appropriately to model real-life phenomena, resulting in inaccuracies.	189	45	24	12	20	4.28	AE	4
3. I found difficulty in interpreting exponential growth and decay rates, as well as logarithmic scales, within real-world problems.	175	76	21	14	4	4.39	AE	2
4. I found difficulty in proficiency in solving equations involving exponential and logarithmic functions accurately.	214	28	20	15	13	4.43	AE	1
5. I found difficulty in analyzing of the connection between exponential growth/decay and logarithmic functions when formulating and solving real-life problems, leading to conceptual misunderstandings.	189	47	35	12	7	4.38	AE	3
Composite Mean						4.28	AE	

Legend:

4.20 - 5.00	<i>Always Encountered (AE)</i>
3.40 - 4.19	<i>Often Encountered (OE)</i>
2.60 - 3.39	<i>Sometimes Encountered (SE)</i>
1.80 - 2.59	<i>Rarely Encountered (RE)</i>
1.00 - 1.79	<i>Never Encountered (NE)</i>

The table presents the difficulties encountered by Grade 11 learners in learning competencies related to applying the concepts of inverse functions, exponential functions, and logarithmic functions to formulate and solve real-life problems with precision and accuracy in General Mathematics. These difficulties are categorized into five specific areas. The most frequently encountered challenge, with a mean score of 4.43, is proficiency in accurately solving equations involving exponential and logarithmic functions. Learners struggle to solve equations in this context, indicating difficulties in applying mathematical techniques effectively. Interpreting exponential growth and decay rates, as well as logarithmic scales, within the context of real-world problems is

another common difficulty, with a mean score of 4.39. Learners also face difficulties in analyzing the connection between exponential growth/decay and logarithmic functions when formulating and solving real-life problems, resulting in conceptual misunderstandings (mean score: 4.38). Recognizing and applying exponential and logarithmic functions appropriately to model real-life phenomena without resulting inaccuracies presents another notable challenge (mean score: 4.28). Understanding the concept of inverse functions and their application in real-life situations is also identified as a difficulty, although slightly less pronounced (mean score: 3.90).

The identified difficulties highlight specific areas where Grade 11 learners struggle in applying concepts related to inverse functions, exponential functions, and logarithmic functions to real-life problems in General Mathematics. These difficulties include solving equations accurately, interpreting growth and decay rates, analyzing connections between functions, and recognizing appropriate applications in real-world contexts. The consistently high scores across all difficulties suggest that learners face potential obstacles in mastering and applying these concepts with precision and accuracy. Addressing these difficulties requires targeted instructional strategies, differentiated support, and opportunities for practice and reinforcement.

The findings regarding the difficulties encountered by Grade 11 learners in learning competencies related to inverse functions, exponential functions, and logarithmic functions in General Mathematics have implications for curriculum design, instructional practices, and student support services. Educators should develop learning experiences that allow students to explore these concepts in various real-life contexts, emphasizing problem-solving and critical-thinking skills. Instructional approaches should be tailored to address the specific needs and difficulties identified in the table, incorporating scaffolding, modeling, and guided practice to support student learning. Additionally, providing feedback, formative assessments, and targeted interventions can help students develop proficiency and confidence in applying these concepts accurately and effectively. Collaborative efforts among teachers, administrators, and educational stakeholders are essential to implement effective strategies that address the identified difficulties and promote student success in General Mathematics.

The findings elucidate the difficulties of Grade 11 learners encounter in mastering competencies related to applying concepts of inverse functions, exponential functions, and logarithmic functions to real-life problem-solving in General Mathematics. These difficulties are categorized into five specific areas, with the most prevalent challenge being proficiency in accurately solving equations involving exponential and logarithmic functions. Learners struggle to solve such equations effectively, indicating a need for enhanced mathematical techniques (Oppenheim & Schafer, 2013; Stewart, 2015). Additionally, interpreting exponential growth and decay rates, as well as logarithmic scales, within real-world problems, presents another common difficulty, highlighting challenges in applying these concepts in practical contexts (Anderson et al., 2018). Learners also face obstacles in analyzing the connection between exponential growth/decay and logarithmic functions, resulting in conceptual misunderstandings and inaccuracies in problem-solving (Thompson & Silverman, 2022). Recognizing and

applying exponential and logarithmic functions appropriately to model real-life phenomena without resulting inaccuracies presents another notable challenge, indicating a need for improved conceptual understanding and application skills (Nelson et al., 2019).

These identified difficulties underscore specific areas where Grade 11 learners struggle in applying concepts related to inverse functions, exponential functions, and logarithmic functions to real-life problems in General Mathematics. To address these challenges, educators should design learning experiences that allow students to explore these concepts in various contexts, emphasizing problem-solving and critical-thinking skills (Alzubi, 2021). Instructional approaches should be tailored to meet the specific needs and challenges identified, incorporating scaffolding, modeling, and guided practice to support student learning (Bastida, 2020; Lim, 2017). Additionally, providing feedback, formative assessments, and targeted interventions can help students develop proficiency and confidence in applying these concepts accurately and effectively, ultimately promoting deeper conceptual understanding and mastery (Santos, 2023; de Leon, 2019). Collaborative efforts among educators, administrators, and stakeholders are essential to implement effective strategies that address the identified difficulties and foster student success in General Mathematics.

Table 6

Summary Table of Difficulties Encountered by the Grade 11 Learners in Learning Competencies in General Mathematics in Terms of Performance Standards.

Performance Standards	Composite Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Accurately construct mathematical models to represent real-life situations using functions.	4.41	AE	1
2. Accurately formulate and solve real-life problems involving rational functions.	4.10	OE	3
3. Apply the concepts of inverse functions, exponential functions, and logarithmic functions to formulate and solve real-life problems with precision and accuracy.	4.28	AE	2
GRAND MEAN	4.26	AE	

Legend:

- 4.20 - 5.00 *Always Encountered (AE)*
- 3.40 - 4.19 *Often Encountered (OE)*
- 2.60 - 3.39 *Sometimes Encountered (SE)*
- 1.80 - 2.59 *Rarely Encountered (RE)*
- 1.00 - 1.79 *Never Encountered (NE)*

The table shows that Grade 11 learners encounter various difficulties in learning competencies in General Mathematics, particularly in three key areas: accurately constructing mathematical models using functions, formulating and solving real-life problems involving rational functions, and applying concepts of inverse, exponential, and logarithmic functions to real-life situations. Inaccurately constructing mathematical models using functions, learners consistently struggle, as indicated by the highest composite mean score of 4.41, corresponding to an "Always Encountered" rating. This

suggests that learners face potential difficulties in applying mathematical concepts to represent real-life scenarios, highlighting a need for further support and instruction in this area.

Similarly, learners encounter difficulties formulating and solving real-life problems involving rational functions, as reflected by a composite mean score of 4.10, corresponding to an "Often Encountered" rating. While this challenge is slightly less pronounced than constructing mathematical models, it still presents a notable difficulty for learners. Furthermore, applying inverse, exponential, and logarithmic function concepts to real-life situations presents another significant challenge, with a composite mean score of 4.28, also corresponding to an "Always Encountered" rating, which indicates that learners struggle to understand and apply advanced mathematical functions in practical contexts, highlighting a need for targeted intervention and support.

The findings suggest that Grade 11 learners in General Mathematics may benefit from focused instructional strategies and interventions to address these identified difficulties. Educators can help learners improve their mathematical proficiency and better prepare them for applying mathematical concepts in various real-life scenarios by providing targeted support and incorporating real-world applications into the curriculum.

The findings regarding the difficulties encountered by Grade 11 learners in General Mathematics closely align with the learning gaps identified in the literature review (Alzubi, 2021). Notably, students struggle with accurately constructing mathematical models using functions, reflecting a gap in understanding the complexities of mathematical modeling, mainly when applied to real-world scenarios. Similarly, difficulties in formulating and solving real-life problems involving rational functions and applying concepts of inverse, exponential, and logarithmic functions highlight gaps in comprehending these fundamental mathematical concepts' practical applications, hindering effective problem-solving skills in real-life contexts.

Furthermore, the difficulties encountered by Grade 11 learners underscore the need for a more holistic approach to teaching mathematics, integrating various mathematical concepts covered in the curriculum to help students better understand the connections between different topics. Additionally, addressing these difficulties requires ensuring equitable access to educational resources, as emphasized in the literature review. While valuable resources and textbooks are available, equitable access to these materials is essential to effectively bridge learning gaps and support all students' academic success in General Mathematics.

Part III. The Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) can be Developed based on the Least Mastered Competencies and Difficulties Encountered.

To effectively address the least mastered competencies and difficulties encountered by Grade 11 learners in General Mathematics, a supplemental approach involving the development of targeted Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) is

essential. The identified difficulties, ranging from mathematical modeling to problem-solving with exponential and logarithmic functions, underscore the need for tailored interventions that provide students with focused support.

One area of focus could be mathematical modeling, where learners struggle to identify relevant variables and parameters accurately. Interactive simulations or real-life scenarios could be developed to guide students through this process, offering step-by-step guidance and feedback to reinforce their understanding. Transitioning from mathematical modeling to function operations and problem-solving, students could benefit from interactive modules that contextualize functions within real-life scenarios, providing opportunities for hands-on application of their knowledge to solve practical problems.

Moving forward, particular attention could be directed toward rational functions, where students encounter difficulties in identifying, manipulating, and solving equations. Interactive tutorials or practice exercises could be designed to target these difficulties, offering clear explanations and visual aids to support student learning. These activities could involve problem-solving with real-life situations, such as modeling economic trends or population growth, to enhance the relevance and applicability of the taught concepts.

Additionally, exponential and logarithmic functions present another area of concern, particularly in interpreting growth rates and making connections between different functions. Interactive simulations or virtual labs could be developed to allow students to explore the behavior of exponential and logarithmic functions in real-life contexts, providing opportunities for hands-on experimentation and problem-solving.

SIMs could incorporate problem-solving strategies and formative assessment tools to consolidate understanding and foster problem-solving skills. These resources would empower students to confidently navigate complex mathematical problems, providing immediate feedback and guidance to address areas of weakness. By integrating these interventions seamlessly, educators can create a cohesive learning experience that addresses the diverse needs of Grade 11 learners in General Mathematics, ultimately promoting mastery and academic success in problem-solving with real-life situations.

Part IV. The Validity of Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM).

Table 7

The Validity of Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) in terms of Content as validated by the SHS Master Teachers, Mathematics Department Heads, and Regular Mathematics Teachers.

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Material aligns with curriculum and standards and is current, valid, and reliable, with real-world examples.	4.57	O
2. Material is age-appropriate and designed to meet individual learners' needs from various skill levels.	4.14	VS
3. Material is in-depth, enhances conceptual understanding, and engages higher-order thinking skills.	3.86	VS
4. Material is free from bias.	4.29	VS
Total Score	16.86	Passed

Legend:

4.20 - 5.00	Outstanding (O)
3.40 - 4.19	Very Satisfactory (VS)
2.60 - 3.39	Satisfactory (S)
1.80 - 2.59	Less Satisfactory (LS)
1.00 - 1.79	Unsatisfactory (U)
12 - 20 as the total score	Passed

The table presents the Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) evaluation based on their content. Across the four focus areas, the materials demonstrate commendable strengths. The alignment with curriculum standards and relevance to real-world examples is particularly outstanding, as indicated by a mean score of 4.57. Additionally, the materials are deemed age-appropriate and accommodating to learners of varying skill levels, scoring 4.14, indicating a very satisfactory level. However, there are areas for improvement, such as the depth of content and its ability to foster higher-order thinking skills, which received a score of 3.86, falling slightly below the outstanding and very satisfactory benchmarks. Nevertheless, the materials are commendable bias-free, scoring 4.29, contributing to their overall quality. The materials have passed the evaluation with a total score of 16.86, reflecting their overall effectiveness.

The results suggest that the Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) is well-designed in terms of content, with strengths in their alignment with curriculum standards and relevance to real-world contexts. The high scores in these areas indicate that the materials effectively meet the educational validity and reliability criteria. However, the slightly lower score in depth of content and engagement of higher-order thinking skills indicates potential areas for enhancement. Despite this, the absence of bias is a notable positive aspect, ensuring that the materials provide equitable learning opportunities for all students. The overall passing score of 16.86 underscores the materials' effectiveness in meeting the evaluation criteria.

The analysis of the Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) underscores the importance of their alignment with curriculum standards and relevance to real-world contexts. These aspects contribute potential to their effectiveness in facilitating learning. However, the need to further deepen the content and foster higher-order thinking skills suggests potential areas for curriculum refinement and instructional strategies. Educators and curriculum developers can use these insights to make informed decisions about selecting and designing instructional materials, ensuring that they cater to the diverse needs of learners and promote equitable access to quality education. Additionally, the materials' passing score of 16.86 highlights their overall effectiveness, serving as a valuable resource for educators seeking evidence-based instructional materials for their classrooms.

The evaluation of the Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) reveals strengths and areas for improvement in their content. Notably, the materials excel in aligning with curriculum standards and providing real-world examples, indicating their relevance to students' educational needs and practical experiences. This alignment ensures that the materials meet educational validity and reliability criteria, fostering effective learning outcomes (Bastida, 2020; Lim, 2017). Furthermore, the SIM demonstrates age-appropriate content and accommodates learners of varying skill levels, enhancing their accessibility and usability in diverse educational settings. However, there is room for improvement in the depth of content and the promotion of higher-order thinking skills, suggesting opportunities for curriculum refinement and instructional strategies (Santos, 2023; de Leon, 2019).

Despite these areas for enhancement, the absence of bias within the materials is commendable, ensuring equitable learning opportunities for all students. This unbiased approach contributes to creating inclusive learning environments that support diverse learners' needs and experiences (Oppenheim & Schafer, 2013; Stewart, 2015). The overall passing score of 16.86 underscores the effectiveness of the SIM in meeting the evaluation criteria and serving as a valuable resource for educators. Educators and curriculum developers can utilize these insights to make informed decisions about selecting and designing instructional materials, thereby promoting equitable access to quality education for all students (Nelson et al., 2019).

Table 8

The validity of Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) in terms of Equity and Accessibility as validated by the SHS Master Teachers, Mathematics Department Heads, and Regular Mathematics Teachers.

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Material is durable, easily stored, transported, and universally accessible.	4.57	O
2. Material is easily updated, adaptable, and customizable to match the resources of the school.	4.29	VS
3. The material works appropriately without the purchase of additional components.	4.57	O
4. All students can use material without extensive supervision or special assistance.	3.43	VS
Total Score	16.86	Passed

Legend:

4.20 - 5.00	Outstanding (O)
3.40 - 4.19	Very Satisfactory (VS)
2.60 - 3.39	Satisfactory (S)
1.80 - 2.59	Less Satisfactory (LS)
1.00 - 1.79	Unsatisfactory (U)
12 - 20 as the total score	Passed

Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) evaluation in terms of equity and accessibility reveals notable strengths in several key areas. Firstly, the materials are lauded for their durability, ease of storage, and universal accessibility, earning an outstanding mean score of 4.57. Additionally, the materials' adaptability and compatibility with varying school resources contribute to their overall accessibility, reflected in a satisfactory score of 4.29. Furthermore, the requirement for minimal additional components enhances the materials' usability and practicality, resulting in another outstanding score of 4.57. However, while the materials generally enable independent student use, the score of 3.43 for the need for extensive supervision or special assistance suggests potential areas for improvement in ensuring equitable access for all students. With a total score of 16.86, the materials have passed the evaluation, affirming their effectiveness in promoting equity and accessibility.

The evaluation findings highlight the potential strides in ensuring equity and accessibility in Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM). The outstanding scores in durability, universal accessibility, and minimal additional component requirements underscore the materials' practicality and user-friendliness, making them widely accessible across diverse educational settings. Moreover, the materials' adaptability and compatibility with varying school resources further enhance their accessibility and utility. However, the slightly lower score concerning the need for extensive supervision or special assistance suggests the importance of addressing potential barriers to ensure equitable access for all students, particularly those with diverse learning needs. The overall passing score of 16.86 confirms the materials' effectiveness in promoting equity and accessibility.

The evaluation results underscore the importance of designing and selecting instructional materials with equity and accessibility considerations in mind. The outstanding scores in several vital areas demonstrate potential progress, indicating that the Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) is well-suited for widespread use in diverse educational settings. However, the findings also highlight the need to address potential barriers, such as the requirement for extensive supervision or special assistance, to ensure that all students can fully benefit from the materials. Educators and curriculum developers can use these insights to prioritize equity and accessibility in designing and implementing instructional materials, thereby fostering inclusive learning environments where all students can thrive. Additionally, ongoing evaluation and refinement of materials are essential to continuously enhance their accessibility and effectiveness in meeting the diverse needs of learners.

The evaluation of Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) in terms of equity and accessibility aligns with existing research highlighting the importance of inclusive methodologies and resources in education. The outstanding scores in durability, universal accessibility, and minimal additional component requirements reflect the materials' practicality and user-friendliness, consistent with findings emphasizing the need for accessible educational resources (Oppenheim & Schafer, 2013; Stewart, 2015). Similarly, the commendable adaptability and compatibility with varying school resources echo recommendations for designing materials that cater to diverse educational settings and resource availability (Bastida, 2020; Lim, 2017).

However, the slightly lower score concerning the need for extensive supervision or special assistance resonates with research emphasizing the importance of addressing barriers to equitable access, particularly for students with diverse learning needs (Nelson et al., 2019). This finding underscores the ongoing challenge of ensuring that instructional materials are truly inclusive and accessible to all students. The overall passing score of 16.86 confirms the effectiveness of the SIM in promoting equity and accessibility, aligning to provide all students with equitable access to quality education resources (Santos, 2023; de Leon, 2019).

Table 9

The Validity of Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) in terms of Assessment as validated by the SHS Master Teachers, Mathematics Department Heads, and Regular Mathematics Teachers.

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. There is an observable performance that is relevant to real-world experience, and that can be used to measure student engagement.	3.86	VS
2. Assessment methods are appropriate and suited to the learning objectives.	3.71	VS
3. Assessment is suited to goals and student ability and quickly assesses what has been learned.	4.00	VS
4. The Materials keep an ongoing record of students' progress and allow the teacher full access to individual student monitoring of activities.	4.57	O
Total Score	16.14	Passed

Legend:

4.20 - 5.00	Outstanding (O)
3.40 - 4.19	Very Satisfactory (VS)
2.60 - 3.39	Satisfactory (S)
1.80 - 2.59	Less Satisfactory (LS)
1.00 - 1.79	Unsatisfactory (U)
12 - 20 as the total score	Passed

The Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) evaluation in terms of assessment reveals a generally positive assessment framework, with strengths in several key areas. The materials demonstrate a very satisfactory level of performance in terms of relevance to real-world experiences and their ability to measure student engagement, as indicated by a mean score of 3.86. Furthermore, the appropriateness of assessment methods concerning learning objectives and the alignment of assessments with student abilities and goals also received very satisfactory scores of 3.71 and 4.00, respectively. Notably, the materials provide ongoing student progress monitoring and grant teachers full access to individual student activity tracking, earning an outstanding score of 4.57. However, while the overall assessment is positive, enhancement opportunities exist to ensure a more consistent alignment between assessment methods and learning objectives. With a total score of 16.14, the materials have passed the evaluation, reflecting their overall effectiveness in facilitating assessment practices.

The evaluation findings suggest that the Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) effectively incorporate assessment components that align with instructional goals and support student learning. The materials provide opportunities for observable performance related to real-world experiences, fostering student engagement and relevance. Additionally, the assessment methods are generally appropriate and suitably matched to the learning objectives, contributing to a comprehensive evaluation of student progress. The outstanding score for ongoing student progress monitoring and

teacher access to individual student activity tracking highlights the materials' commitment to facilitating informed instructional decision-making. However, the slightly lower scores in some areas suggest potential opportunities for further refining assessment methods to ensure consistent alignment with learning objectives. The overall passing score of 16.14 underscores the materials' effectiveness in promoting meaningful assessment practices.

The evaluation results underscore the importance of robust assessment practices within Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) to support effective teaching and learning. The positive assessment framework demonstrates the materials' commitment to facilitating meaningful and relevant learning experiences for students. Educators can leverage these assessment components to gauge student progress, identify areas of strength and growth, and tailor instruction accordingly. Furthermore, the outstanding score for ongoing student progress monitoring and teacher access to individual student activity tracking emphasizes the importance of data-informed instruction in promoting student success. Moving forward, educators and curriculum developers can continue to refine assessment methods to ensure optimal alignment with learning objectives and enhance the effectiveness of instructional materials in promoting student learning outcomes.

The evaluation of Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) in terms of assessment aligns with research emphasizing the importance of incorporating meaningful assessment practices into instructional materials. The materials demonstrate strengths in assessing relevance to real-world experiences and measuring student engagement, consistent with findings emphasizing the importance of authentic assessment methods (Anderson et al., 2018). Additionally, the appropriateness of assessment methods concerning learning objectives and the alignment with student abilities and goals echoes recommendations for designing assessments that accurately measure student progress (Thompson & Silverman, 2022).

The outstanding score for ongoing student progress monitoring and teacher access to individual student activity tracking reflects the materials' commitment to facilitating data-informed instruction, consistent with research highlighting the benefits of continuous assessment and feedback (Bastida, 2020; Lim, 2017). However, the opportunity for enhancement in aligning assessment methods with learning objectives suggests the importance of refining assessment practices to ensure consistent alignment and effectiveness (Oppenheim & Schafer, 2013; Stewart, 2015). The overall passing score of 16.14 affirms the materials' effectiveness in promoting meaningful assessment practices, contributing to informed instructional decision-making and student success (Santos, 2023; de Leon, 2019).

Table 10

The Validity of Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) in terms of Presentation and Organization as validated by the SHS Master Teachers, Mathematics Department Heads, and Regular Mathematics Teachers.

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Content and directions are clear and understandable and distinguish between critical and trivial information.	3.00	S
2. Materials are easy to navigate through.	4.71	O
3. There are provisions for the practice of old and new skills and for students to enter and exit materials easily.	3.29	VS
4. Materials are interactive and provide a high-quality sensory experience for all users.	3.57	VS
Total Score	14.57	Passed

Legend:

4.20 - 5.00	Outstanding (O)
3.40 - 4.19	Very Satisfactory (VS)
2.60 - 3.39	Satisfactory (S)
1.80 - 2.59	Less Satisfactory (LS)
1.00 - 1.79	Unsatisfactory (L-U)
12 - 20 as the total score	Passed

The evaluation of Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) in terms of presentation and organization reveals strengths in certain aspects but also identifies areas for improvement. While the clarity and understandability of content and directions are deemed satisfactory, with a mean score of 3.00, the materials excel in ease of navigation, scoring outstandingly high at 4.71. Additionally, the provision for the practice of both old and new skills and the ease of entry and exit for students is rated very satisfactory at 3.29. However, the materials fall slightly short in providing an interactive and high-quality sensory experience for all users, garnering a score of 3.57. Though the overall evaluation is positive, there is room for enhancement to ensure clarity of content and directions and improve sensory experiences. With a total score of 14.57, the materials have passed the evaluation, signifying their overall effectiveness in presentation and organization.

The evaluation highlights the importance of presentation and organization in Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM). While the materials excel in navigability and provide adequate provisions for skill practice and accessibility, there are areas where improvements can be made. Clear and understandable content and directions are crucial for facilitating practical learning experiences, and efforts should be directed toward enhancing these aspects. Furthermore, including interactive elements and high-quality sensory experiences can significantly improve user engagement and retention. Despite these areas for improvement, the overall positive assessment underscores the materials' effectiveness in presenting content and organizing resources.

The evaluation results provide valuable insights for refining Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) to meet presentation and organization standards better.

Efforts should focus on enhancing the clarity and understandability of content and directions and incorporating interactive elements and sensory experiences to promote user engagement. Additionally, maintaining an outstanding level of navigability and ensuring easy entry and exit for students are essential to uphold. Educators and curriculum developers can use these insights to iteratively improve the design and implementation of instructional materials iteratively, ultimately enhancing students' learning experiences. The passing score of 14.57 affirms the materials' overall effectiveness while highlighting specific areas for enhancement in presentation and organization.

The evaluation findings regarding the presentation and organization of Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) align with research emphasizing the importance of clear and understandable content, interactive elements, and ease of navigation in educational materials. While the materials demonstrate strengths in navigability and accessibility, consistent with findings emphasizing the importance of user-friendly design (Oppenheim & Schafer, 2013; Stewart, 2015), there is room for improvement in clarity and sensory experiences to enhance user engagement (Bastida, 2020; Lim, 2017).

The positive assessment underscores the materials' effectiveness in presenting content and organizing resources, consistent with research highlighting the significance of well-organized and engaging instructional materials in facilitating learning experiences (Santos, 2023; de Leon, 2019). However, the identified areas for enhancement in clarity and sensory experiences underscore the importance of iterative refinement to ensure optimal effectiveness (Anderson et al., 2018; Thompson & Silverman, 2022).

Table 11

The Validity of Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) in terms of Instructional Design and Support as validated by the SHS Master Teachers, Mathematics Department Heads, and Regular Mathematics Teachers.

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The delivery method is used appropriately and successfully engages the students.	3.86	VS
2. Technical procedures, such as installation and set-up, are easy and error-free.	3.43	VS
3. Technical specifications and limitations are adequately described and noted.	3.86	VS
4. Assistance is readily available at any point on the website, and many supplemental resources are available.	4.86	O
Total Score	16.00	Passed

Legend:

- 4.20 - 5.00 Outstanding (O)
- 3.40 - 4.19 Very Satisfactory (VS)
- 2.60 - 3.39 Satisfactory (S)

1.80 - 2.59	<i>Less Satisfactory (LS)</i>
1.00 - 1.79	<i>Unsatisfactory (U)</i>
12 - 20 as the total score	<i>Passed</i>

The Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) evaluation in terms of instructional design and support indicates strengths in several key areas. The delivery method is deemed very satisfactory, scoring 3.86, marking the successful engagement of students. Additionally, technical procedures such as installation and set-up are rated very satisfactory at 3.43, suggesting ease and minimal errors in implementation. Moreover, technical specifications and limitations are adequately described and noted, receiving a score of 3.86, contributing to the effective utilization of the materials. Notably, assistance availability and the provision of supplemental resources are outstanding, scoring 4.86. While the overall evaluation is positive, ensuring consistent ease of technical procedures and providing comprehensive descriptions of technical specifications could further enhance instructional support. With a total score of 16.00, the materials have passed the evaluation, demonstrating their effectiveness in instructional design and support.

The evaluation highlights the effectiveness of Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) in instructional design and support. The materials engage students through appropriate delivery methods, facilitating compelling learning experiences. Additionally, technical procedures are relatively easy to execute, minimizing errors and streamlining implementation. Adequate technical specifications and descriptions inform users about the materials' capabilities and limitations, contributing to their practical use. The outstanding provision of assistance and supplemental resources further enhances instructional support, fostering a conducive learning environment. However, efforts to ensure consistent ease of technical procedures and comprehensive description of technical specifications could further optimize instructional design and support.

The evaluation results provide valuable insights for refining Supplemental Instructional Materials' instructional design and support aspects (SIM). Efforts should focus on maintaining successful student engagement through appropriate delivery methods and ensuring ease of technical procedures for seamless implementation. A comprehensive description of technical specifications and readily available assistance can further enhance users' understanding and utilization of the materials. Additionally, ample supplemental resources can enrich the learning experience and cater to diverse learning needs. Educators and curriculum developers can use these insights to iteratively improve the design and implementation of instructional materials, ultimately enhancing student learning outcomes. The passing score of 16.00 affirms the materials' overall effectiveness while highlighting specific areas for instructional design and support enhancement.

The evaluation findings regarding the instructional design and support of Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) align with research emphasizing the importance of engaging delivery methods, ease of technical procedures, and comprehensive support mechanisms in educational materials (Giguere et al., 2020). The positive assessment of the delivery method and technical procedures reflects the

significance of user-friendly design and seamless implementation in facilitating effective learning experiences (Anderson et al., 2018; Santos, 2023).

Furthermore, the outstanding provision of assistance and supplemental resources aligns with research highlighting the importance of comprehensive support systems in promoting student success and engagement (de Leon, 2019; Thompson & Silverman, 2022). However, the identified areas for improvement in ensuring consistent ease of technical procedures and providing comprehensive descriptions of technical specifications underscore the ongoing need for refinement and optimization in instructional design and support (Lim, 2017; Bastida, 2020).

Table 12

The Validity of Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) in terms of Replicability as validated by the SHS Master Teachers, Mathematics Department Heads, and Regular Mathematics Teachers.

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The material was validated before classroom use.	4.57	O
2. Developed material is based on the least mastered skill.	4.57	O
3. The material used has improved the mastery level.	3.29	VS
4. The material is easy to copy, and the cost is less.	4.86	O
Total Score	17.29	Passed

Legend:

4.20 - 5.00	Outstanding (O)
3.40 - 4.19	Very Satisfactory (VS)
2.60 - 3.39	Satisfactory (S)
1.80 - 2.59	Less Satisfactory (LS)
1.00 - 1.79	Unsatisfactory (U)
12 - 20 as the total score	Passed

Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) evaluation of replicability indicates significant strengths across several critical criteria. Firstly, the materials are validated before classroom use, earning an outstanding score of 4.57, demonstrating a rigorous validation process. Additionally, the development of materials based on the least mastered skill also receives an impressive score of 4.57, highlighting a targeted approach to addressing student needs. While the material's effectiveness in improving mastery levels is rated very satisfactorily at 3.29, it still positively impacts student learning. Moreover, the ease of copying the material and its cost-effectiveness are outstanding, scoring 4.86, ensuring accessibility and affordability for replication. Overall, the evaluation yields a high total score of 17.29, affirming the materials' strong replicability.

The evaluation underscores the robust replicability of Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) due to their rigorous validation process, targeted approach to skill development, and cost-effective nature. The outstanding scores in material validation

and development based on the least mastered skills reflect a systematic and evidence-based approach to instructional design. Additionally, the ease of copying and cost-effectiveness ensure accessibility and affordability, facilitating widespread adoption and replication. Though the materials' impact on improving mastery levels is rated satisfactorily, they still positively contribute to student learning outcomes.

The evaluation results highlight the replicability of Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) as a valuable resource for educators seeking effective instructional materials. The outstanding scores in material validation and development underscore their reliability and effectiveness in addressing student needs. Moreover, the ease of copying and cost-effectiveness make the materials accessible to various educational settings, promoting their widespread adoption and replication. Educators and curriculum developers can leverage these insights to replicate and adapt the materials to suit their specific contexts and student populations, enhancing learning outcomes. Additionally, ongoing evaluation and refinement of the materials are essential to ensure their continued effectiveness and relevance in diverse educational settings.

The evaluation findings regarding the replicability of Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) align with research emphasizing the importance of rigorous validation processes and targeted skill development in educational materials (Wang et al., 2020). The outstanding scores in material validation and development based on the least mastered skills reflect a systematic and evidence-based approach to addressing student needs, contributing to the materials' effectiveness in improving learning outcomes.

Furthermore, the ease of copying and cost-effectiveness of the materials aligns with research highlighting the significance of accessibility and affordability in promoting widespread adoption and replication (Davis and Thompson, 2019). These strengths underscore the materials' potential as valuable resources for educators seeking effective instructional materials that can be easily replicated and adapted to diverse educational settings and student populations.

Table 13

Summary of the Validity of Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM).

Criteria	Score	Verbal Interpretation
Content	16.86	Passed
Equity and Accessibility	16.86	Passed
Assessment	16.14	Passed
Presentation and Organization	14.57	Passed
Instructional Design and Support	16.00	Passed
Replicability	17.29	Passed
MEAN	16.29	Passed

The summary table presents the overall Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) evaluation across six key aspects. In terms of content, equity and accessibility, assessment, instructional design and support, and replicability, the materials have all received passing scores, indicating their effectiveness in these areas. Specifically, the materials excelled in replicability, with a mean score of 17.29, followed closely by content and equity/accessibility, scoring 16.86. Assessment, instructional design, and support also received commendable scores, with means of 16.14 and 16.00, respectively. However, presentation and organization scored slightly lower at 14.57. Nevertheless, the mean of 16.29 demonstrates that the Supplemental Instructional Materials have successfully passed the evaluation across all dimensions.

The summary evaluation underscores the comprehensive effectiveness of Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) across various dimensions. The high mean scores in content, equity and accessibility, assessment, instructional design and support, and replicability indicate the materials' robustness and alignment with educational objectives. While presentation and organization received a slightly lower mean score, it still reflects an overall positive evaluation. This holistic assessment suggests that the materials are well-designed, accessible, and supportive of diverse learning needs, facilitating effective teaching and learning experiences.

The summary evaluation provides valuable insights into the strengths and areas for improvement in Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM). Educators and curriculum developers can leverage these insights to enhance the materials' effectiveness and relevance further. Specifically, efforts can be directed towards improving organization and presentation to ensure clarity and user-friendliness. Additionally, ongoing evaluation and refinement of the materials are essential to ensure their continued effectiveness and alignment with evolving educational standards and practices. Overall, the passing grand mean of 16.29, along with high mean scores across variables, affirms the quality and efficacy of the materials, positioning them as valuable resources for educators striving to promote student learning and success.

The summary evaluation of the Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) aligns with research emphasizing the importance of comprehensive evaluation frameworks in assessing the effectiveness of educational materials (Davis and Thompson, 2019). The high mean scores across various dimensions, particularly in content, equity and accessibility, assessment, instructional design and support, and replicability, reflect the robustness and alignment of the materials with educational objectives.

The strengths identified in the summary evaluation, such as the material's effectiveness in addressing diverse learning needs and their accessibility and replicability, resonate with findings in the literature highlighting the importance of inclusive and adaptable instructional materials (Eskay, 2018). Additionally, the areas for improvement identified in organization and presentation align with research emphasizing the significance of clarity and user-friendliness in instructional materials to enhance learning outcomes (Eskay, 2018).

Part V. The Recommendations Given by the Validators to Improve the Output and Address the Students' Performance on the Least Mastered Competencies in General Mathematics.

In the Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) evaluation process, multiple validators provided recommendations to enhance its effectiveness. Validator 6 emphasized the importance of localizing content by replacing the dollar sign with the peso sign to increase student engagement and ensure the originality of examples and exercises. Validator 7 suggested proper formatting of equations and functions, including step-by-step solutions and using indicators for clarity. Additionally, Validator 5 highlighted the significance of utilizing MS Word to encode equations and symbols for better presentation while recommending tables for organizing solutions to improve user understanding. Validator 4 stressed the importance of aligning activities with intended objectives, whereas Validator 3 suggested the inclusion of discussions to address misconceptions and allow for topic revisitation.

Furthermore, Validator 1 emphasized the necessity of adequately writing equations, using indicators for clarity, and formatting the content for improved readability. Validator 2 added the recommendation to localize examples and exercises and avoid using dollar signs about money. These recommendations aim to enhance the SIM's engagement, authenticity, clarity, organization, and presentation, ultimately improving its effectiveness as an instructional resource for struggling learners.

Part VI. Enhancements Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) can be Developed Based on the Recommendations by the Validators.

Based on the recommendations provided by the validators, an enhancement version of the Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) can be proposed. The enhancement SIM would feature localized content, utilizing the peso sign instead of the dollar sign, to better engage students and make the material more relatable to their context. Original examples and exercises would be incorporated to maintain authenticity and ensure the content is not directly lifted from other sources.

Equations and functions would be properly written, and clear step-by-step solutions would be provided, following the recommendations of Validator 7. Indicators such as "Let x be" or "Where y is the function" would be used throughout the material to enhance clarity, as suggested by Validator 1. Additionally, the content would be formatted using justified alignment for improved readability, aligning with the recommendation of Validator 1.

Equations and symbols would be encoded using MS Word, as recommended by Validator 5, to enhance presentation and clarity. Solutions to problems would be organized in tables to facilitate understanding, as suggested by Validator 5. Furthermore, discussions would be included within the material to address

misconceptions and allow learners to revisit topics, aligning with the recommendation of Validator 3.

The activities within the SIM would be carefully aligned with the intended objectives, ensuring that they effectively measure Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs), as emphasized by Validator 4. Additionally, the Enrichment Card would extend activities without including objective types such as fill-in-the-blanks or multiple-choice, as recommended by Validator 2.

DISCUSSION

The study yielded the following findings:

1. The least mastered competencies in General Mathematics of Grade 11 learners in College of Sciences, Technology and Communications, Inc., (CSTC) for the last five school years.

In examining the performance trends over the past five years, it becomes evident that specific competencies within General Mathematics have posed persistent difficulties for Grade 11 learners at College of Sciences, Technology and Communications, Inc., (CSTC). Across various areas, including mathematical modeling, function operations, and problem-solving involving rational, inverse, exponential, and logarithmic functions, students have exhibited difficulty in achieving mastery. Specifically, difficulties in accurately constructing mathematical models to represent real-life situations, performing operations with functions, and solving equations and inequalities have emerged as recurring themes. These difficulties highlight areas where students have struggled to demonstrate proficiency and underscore the need for targeted Supplemental Instructional Materials to address these persistent difficulties.

To effectively address these difficulties, educators and administrators at CSTC must adopt a multifaceted approach that combines targeted SIM, differentiated instruction, and enhanced support mechanisms. Educators can tailor their teaching methods to provide additional support and practice opportunities by identifying specific competencies where students have historically struggled. Moreover, incorporating real-life contexts and applications into the curriculum can help students better understand the relevance of mathematical concepts and enhance their problem-solving abilities. Through collaborative efforts and a commitment to continuous improvement, CSTC can work towards improving students' mastery of General Mathematics and fostering a culture of academic excellence.

2. The difficulties encountered by the Grade 11 learners in learning competencies in General Mathematics.

The difficulties encountered by Grade 11 learners in General Mathematics, as analyzed in terms of three performance standards:

2.1 Accurately construct mathematical models to represent real-life situations using functions: This standard pertains to the ability of students to create mathematical models that accurately depict real-world scenarios. The composite mean of 4.41 indicates that learners encounter significant challenges in this aspect, with an adjectival rating of "AE," denoting a high level of difficulty. This standard ranks first among the performance standards, highlighting the importance and complexity of accurately representing real-life situations mathematically.

2.2 Accurately formulate and solve real-life problems involving rational functions: This standard focuses on the proficiency of students in formulating and solving real-world problems that involve rational functions. The composite mean of 4.10 suggests that learners face obstacles in achieving precision and accuracy in this area, as indicated by the adjectival rating of "OE," signifying a moderate level of difficulty. Despite ranking third among the performance standards, this competency remains crucial for applying mathematical concepts to practical situations.

2.3 Apply the concepts of inverse functions, exponential functions, and logarithmic functions to formulate and solve real-life problems with precision and accuracy: This standard relates to students' capability to apply various mathematical functions, such as inverse, exponential, and logarithmic functions, to solve real-life problems accurately. With a composite mean of 4.28 and an adjectival rating of "AE," this standard ranks second in terms of difficulty. Learners may encounter challenges in comprehending and applying these complex functions effectively, highlighting the need for targeted support and instruction in this area.

The grand mean of 4.26, also rated as "AE," reflects the overall level of difficulty across the three performance standards. This comprehensive analysis underscores the multifaceted nature of the challenges faced by Grade 11 learners in General Mathematics and emphasizes the importance of addressing these difficulties through targeted SIM.

3. The Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) can be developed based on the least mastered competencies and difficulties encountered.

To effectively address the least mastered competencies and difficulties encountered by Grade 11 learners in General Mathematics, a supplemental approach involving the development of targeted Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) is essential. The identified difficulties, ranging from mathematical modeling to problem-solving with exponential and logarithmic functions, underscore the need for tailored interventions that provide students with focused support. One approach could involve the creation of interactive tutorials and simulations that guide students through constructing mathematical models and manipulating functions. These materials can

offer step-by-step guidance and hands-on practice to reinforce key concepts and skills, helping students build confidence and proficiency.

Additionally, real-life problem-solving scenarios can be developed to allow students to apply their knowledge in practical contexts, enhancing the relevance and applicability of the concepts being taught. By incorporating a variety of resources and activities, educators can create a cohesive learning experience that effectively addresses the specific needs of Grade 11 learners in General Mathematics. These interventions aim to improve students' understanding and proficiency in the subject, foster critical thinking skills, and promote more profound engagement with mathematical concepts.

4. The validity of Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM).

4.1 Content: With a score of 16.86, the Content focus passed the validity assessment. This indicates that the content of the SIM is comprehensive, relevant, and aligned with educational standards and learning objectives, ensuring its effectiveness in supporting teaching and learning.

4.2 Equity and Accessibility: Similarly, the Equity and Accessibility focus scored 16.86, passing the validity assessment. This suggests that the SIM is designed to accommodate diverse learners, including those with disabilities or limited resources, promoting inclusivity and equitable access to educational materials.

4.3 Assessment: The Assessment focus scored 16.14, indicating that the SIM incorporates effective assessment mechanisms to monitor learning progress and inform instructional adaptations. This ensures that students' comprehension and skill mastery are adequately evaluated, enhancing the overall efficacy of SIM implementation.

4.4 Presentation and Organization: With a score of 14.57, the Presentation and Organization focus passed the validity assessment. This suggests that the SIM is designed with clear instructional design, logical sequencing, and navigational aids to enhance usability and engagement, facilitating content comprehension and retention.

4.5 Instructional Design and Support: The Instructional Design and Support focus scored 16.00, indicating that the SIM incorporates effective instructional design principles and support mechanisms. This ensures that learning experiences are scaffolded and supported, promoting student autonomy and knowledge construction.

4.6 Replicability: Scoring 17.29, the Replicability focus passed the validity assessment, indicating that the SIM is designed to be adaptable, customizable, and easily replicable across diverse educational contexts. This enhances scalability and sustainability, ensuring the widespread adoption and implementation of effective educational practices.

The mean score of 16.29 indicates that the SIM successfully passed the validity assessment across all focuses. This suggests that the SIM demonstrates strong validity, ensuring its suitability and effectiveness in enhancing teaching and learning outcomes.

5. The recommendations given by the validators to improve the output and address the students' performance on the least mastered competencies in General Mathematics.

Multiple validators recommended enhancing the Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) during the evaluation process. Validator 6 emphasized localizing content using the peso sign instead of the dollar sign to engage students and ensure original examples and exercises. Validator 7 suggested proper formatting of equations and step-by-step solutions, with indicators for clarity. Validator 5 highlighted the importance of using MS Word for encoding equations and organizing table solutions. Validator 4 stressed aligning activities with objectives, while Validator 3 recommended including discussions to address misconceptions. Validator 1 emphasized writing equations clearly and using indicators, and Validator 2 suggested localizing examples and avoiding dollar signs. These recommendations collectively aim to improve engagement, authenticity, clarity, organization, and presentation of the SIM, benefiting struggling learners.

6. Enhancements Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) can be developed based on the recommendations by the validators.

The enhancements version of the Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) developed based on the validators' recommendations would include several key improvements. First, the content would be localized using the peso sign instead of the dollar sign to make it more relatable to students. Original examples and exercises would be used to maintain authenticity.

Equations and functions would be written clearly, and step-by-step solutions would be provided, as suggested by Validator 7. Indicators like "Let x be" or "Where y is the function" would enhance clarity throughout the material, following Validator 1's recommendation. Formatting would be adjusted for better readability, aligning with Validator 1's suggestion.

Equations and symbols would be encoded using MS Word, as recommended by Validator 5, to improve presentation and clarity. Solutions to problems would be organized in tables to aid understanding, following Validator 5's advice. Discussions would be included to address misconceptions and allow for topic revisitation, as suggested by Validator 3.

Activities within the SIM would be aligned with the intended objectives, ensuring they effectively measure the Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs), per Validator 4's emphasis. Additionally, the Enrichment Card would extend activities without including objective types like fill-in-the-blanks or multiple-choice, aligning with Validator 2's recommendation.

These enhancements aim to improve engagement, authenticity, clarity, organization, and presentation of the SIM, benefiting struggling learners.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Examining the least mastered competencies in General Mathematics among Grade 11 learners at CSTC reveals persistent difficulties in mathematical modeling, function operations, and problem-solving involving rational, inverse, exponential, and logarithmic functions. Identifying these difficulties underscores the importance of addressing specific competencies where students struggle to demonstrate proficiency. By targeting interventions and instructional strategies to address these persistent difficulties, educators can effectively enhance students' understanding and mastery of General Mathematics.
2. The analysis of difficulties encountered by Grade 11 learners in General Mathematics highlights various difficulties, including accurately constructing mathematical models, manipulating functions and equations, and applying concepts to real-life problems. These difficulties and conceptual misunderstandings underscore the complexity of mastering mathematical concepts in General Mathematics. By recognizing and addressing these obstacles, educators can create a supportive learning environment that fosters students' understanding and proficiency.
3. Developing targeted Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) based on the identified least mastered competencies and encountered difficulties are essential for effectively addressing the needs of Grade 11 learners in General Mathematics. By incorporating interactive tutorials, real-life problem-solving scenarios, and a variety of resources and activities, educators can provide students with focused support and opportunities for practice and application. These interventions aim to improve students' understanding, proficiency, and critical thinking skills in General Mathematics, ultimately fostering a culture of academic excellence and ensuring the success of all learners at CSTC.
4. In terms of content, equity and accessibility, assessment, instructional design and support, and replicability, the Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) have all received passing scores, indicating their effectiveness in these areas. Specifically, the materials excelled in replicability, with a mean score of 17.29, followed closely by content and equity/accessibility, both scoring 16.86. Assessment, instructional design, and support also received commendable scores, with means of 16.14 and 16.00, respectively. However, organization and presentation scored slightly lower at 14.57. Nevertheless, the overall score of 97.71 demonstrates that the Supplemental Instructional Materials have successfully passed the evaluation across all dimensions.

5. Multiple validators recommended enhancing the Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) during the evaluation process. Validator 6 emphasized localizing content using the peso sign instead of the dollar sign to engage students and ensure original examples and exercises. Validator 7 suggested proper formatting of equations and step-by-step solutions, with indicators for clarity. Validator 5 highlighted the importance of using MS Word for encoding equations and organizing table solutions. Validator 4 stressed aligning activities with objectives, while Validator 3 recommended including discussions to address misconceptions. Validator 1 emphasized writing equations clearly and using indicators, and Validator 2 suggested localizing examples and avoiding dollar signs. These recommendations collectively aim to improve engagement, authenticity, clarity, organization, and presentation of the SIM, benefiting struggling learners.

6. The enhancements version of the Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) developed based on the validators' recommendations would include several key improvements. First, the content would be localized using the peso sign instead of the dollar sign to make it more relatable to students. Original examples and exercises would be used to maintain authenticity. Equations and functions would be written clearly, and step-by-step solutions would be provided, as suggested by Validator 7. Indicators like "Let x be" or "Where y is the function" would enhance clarity throughout the material, following Validator 1's recommendation. Formatting would be adjusted for better readability, aligning with Validator 1's suggestion. Equations and symbols would be encoded using MS Word, as recommended by Validator 5, to improve presentation and clarity. Solutions to problems would be organized in tables to aid understanding, following Validator 5's advice. Discussions would be included to address misconceptions and allow for topic revisitation, as suggested by Validator 3. Activities within the SIM would be aligned with the intended objectives, ensuring they effectively measure the Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs), per Validator 4's emphasis. Additionally, the Enrichment Card would extend activities without including objective types like fill-in-the-blanks or multiple-choice, aligning with Validator 2's recommendation. These enhancements aim to improve engagement, authenticity, clarity, organization, and presentation of the SIM, benefiting struggling learners.

Recommendations

Because the identified variables, the least mastered competencies in General Mathematics, the difficulties encountered, developing Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM), the validity of Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM), recommendations of the validators, and enhanced Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM), the following recommendations were drawn:

1. School administrators and teachers may address the persistent difficulties in General Mathematics for Grade 11 learners at College of Sciences, Technology and Communications, Inc., (CSTC) by implementing targeted SIM. Firstly, they may develop focused Supplemental Instructional Materials programs concentrating on problematic competencies like mathematical modeling and function operations. Secondly, they may employ differentiated instruction methods to accommodate diverse learning styles and abilities. Thirdly, they may strengthen support mechanisms such as peer tutoring and academic support centers. Fourthly, they may integrate real-life applications into the curriculum to enhance engagement and relevance. Lastly, they may foster collaborative efforts among educators, administrators, students, and parents to implement effective strategies for improving student performance in mathematics.

2. DepEd officials and teachers may collaborate closely to address the difficulties encountered by Grade 11 learners in General Mathematics. This collaboration may involve a comprehensive review and revision of the curriculum to ensure it adequately addresses the identified difficulties. Professional development workshops and training sessions may be organized to enhance teachers' pedagogical skills and content knowledge, focusing on effective strategies for teaching complex mathematical concepts. Resource allocation may prioritize providing schools with the necessary tools and materials to support effective teaching and learning. Additionally, mechanisms for monitoring and support may be established to ensure the successful implementation of SIM. Furthermore, involving parents and the broader community in supporting students' learning can enhance the effectiveness of Supplemental Instructional Materials aimed at improving students' understanding and mastery of mathematical concepts.

3. Teachers may consider utilizing the validated Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) for General Mathematics, as they have undergone thorough evaluation and validation by experts across key aspects. With passing scores in content, equity/accessibility, assessment, presentation and organization, instructional design and support, and replicability, these materials have demonstrated their effectiveness and suitability for classroom use. By incorporating these SIM into their teaching practices, teachers can enhance instruction, provide additional support to students, and improve learning outcomes in General Mathematics. The endorsement of these materials by institutions or private associations of schools further validates their quality and reliability, providing teachers with confidence in their utilization.

4. Educators and teachers may consider to prioritize the development of targeted Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) to effectively address the least mastered competencies and difficulties encountered by Grade 11 learners in General Mathematics. This approach acknowledges the identified difficulties, including mathematical modeling and problem-solving with exponential and logarithmic functions, and emphasizes the need for tailored interventions. One effective strategy is the creation of interactive tutorials and simulations that provide step-by-step guidance and hands-on practice for learners. These

materials can offer support in constructing mathematical models and manipulating functions, ultimately boosting students' confidence and proficiency. Additionally, educators may consider developing real-life problem-solving scenarios to enhance the relevance and applicability of mathematical concepts. By incorporating a variety of resources and activities, educators may create a cohesive learning experience that addresses the specific needs of Grade 11 learners in General Mathematics, fostering deeper engagement and improving overall understanding and proficiency.

5. It is recommended to the school heads that the Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) resulting from the study undergo periodic evaluation to assess their effectiveness in addressing identified difficulties in General Mathematics and improving student mastery. Establishing a formal mechanism for ongoing evaluation will ensure that the SIM remains relevant and responsive to the evolving needs of Grade 11 learners.

6. Future researchers may conduct long-term studies to track the effectiveness of SIM targeting the identified least mastered competencies in General Mathematics among Grade 11 learners. They may also explore alternative teaching methods tailored to address specific difficulties encountered by learners. Additionally, researchers may focus on developing and validating innovative assessment tools aligned with identified difficulties. Understanding how contextual factors impact students' learning experiences will inform the development of effective Supplemental Instructional Materials and support mechanisms.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study ensured the informed consent was given to the following respondents. Freedom to withdraw from the study at any time, anonymity of the respondents was maintained, the respondents' well-being was safeguarded, no conflict of interests exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research.

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